

**MEMORY AND METAMEMORY IN EVERYDAY SETTINGS: ASSESSING
RECALL, RECOGNITION, AND NAMING USING CAR BRAND LOGOS**

Julia Mayas*¹, Antonio Prieto*², and Pedro R. Montoro*²

¹ Dpto. Psicología Básica II. Facultad de Psicología, UNED

² Dpto. Psicología Básica I. Facultad de Psicología, UNED

*Corresponding author information:

Julia Mayas, C/ Juan del Rosal 10. Dpto. Psicología Básica II. Facultad de Psicología
UNED. Spain (e-mail: jmayas@psi.uned.es).

Antonio Prieto, C/ Juan del Rosal 10. Dpto. Psicología Básica I. Facultad de Psicología
UNED. Spain (e-mail: antonioprieto@psi.uned.es).

Pedro R. Montoro, C/ Juan del Rosal 10. Dpto. Psicología Básica I. Facultad de
Psicología UNED. Spain (e-mail: prmontoro@psi.uned.es).

Abstract

Previous research on incidental memory in everyday settings has shown that frequent exposure to stimuli does not guarantee accurate representation in memory. In two studies, we explored the memory and metamemory of car brand logos using recall (drawing) and recognition tasks (Study 1) or a naming task (Study 2). The results showed that memory accuracy for logos was modest in the recall and recognition tasks; nevertheless, the participants' accuracy in naming the visually displayed car logos was almost perfect. The participants showed overconfidence in their ability to recall and recognize car logos prior to their performance, which was adjusted after completing the recall task. Overconfidence was absent in the naming tasks. These results replicate the modest visual memory and metacognitive adjustments in recall and recognition tasks found in previous studies and contrast with participants' better memory performance and metacognitive adjustments in the naming task.

Keywords: Memory, Logos, Metamemory, Recall, Recognition, Naming.

1. Introduction

In the marketing arena, designers make significant efforts to create highly identifiable and discerning logos that have a powerful impact on consumers. Logos are usually designed to be easily associated with the brand they represent, memorable, recognizable, and particularly distinguishable from other logos (see Park et al., 2013, for a review). Specifically, car brand logos represent a large sample of these characteristics. Moreover, in modern societies, they are stimuli with which we interact repeatedly in everyday real-world settings, making them suitable for the study of incidental memories of everyday objects.

Previous research in this area has shown that, contrary to expectations, people usually struggle when they have to remember the visual details of everyday objects despite their frequent contact with them (see Castel et al., 2015, for a review). This seems inconsistent with the traditional body of research showing both a great capacity for visual detail in long-term memory (e.g., Brady et al., 2008; Mandler & Ritchey, 1977) and improved memory for stimuli to which we are repeatedly exposed (e.g., Ebbinghaus, 1964; Palumbo et al., 2021).

Two classical studies (Nickerson & Adams, 1979; Rubin & Kontis, 1983) pioneered the research in this field. In their 1979 study, Nickerson and Adams explored the visual memory of a US penny using various tasks and found consistently poor performance. One experiment showed an average recall of only three out of eight features of the penny, with one participant, a penny collector, recalling all the features. In a separate task, less than half of the participants (15 out of 36) correctly identified the genuine penny drawing among the 15 options, despite it being more frequently recognized than the counterfeits. Their results indicated poor memory for the visual details of coins, which the authors interpreted as due to the use of a common memory scheme based on generic averaged properties (see also Jones & Martin, 1992). Since this initial work, a large number of studies have been conducted using a wide variety of stimuli, tasks, and contexts to assess the memory of everyday objects (see Table 1).

Table1.

Summary of the main contributions of incidental memory studies of everyday settings.

Author/s (year)	Stimuli
<i>Blake & Castel (2019)</i>	Flags of countries
<i>Blake et al., (2015)</i>	The Apple logo
<i>Castel et al., (2012)</i>	The position of fire extinguishers at workplaces
<i>French & Richards (1993)</i>	Standard clock with numbers (Roman numerals)
<i>Hargis et al., (2018)</i>	Covers of university textbooks
<i>Jones (1990)</i>	Face direction of coins
<i>Jones & Martin (1992)</i>	Coin features
<i>Iancu & Iancu (2017)</i>	The Apple logo
<i>Liu et al., (2010)</i>	Letters on keyboards
<i>Marmie & Healy (2004)</i>	Coin features
<i>Martin & Jones (1998)</i>	Aspects of road signs
<i>Misra et al., (2018)</i>	Real-life events
<i>Montoro & Ruiz (2022)</i>	Famous ornamental monument
<i>Murphy & Castel (2021)</i>	Familiar building
<i>Nickerson and Adams (1972)</i>	Coin features
<i>Rinck (1999)</i>	Numerical keypads of calculators and telephones
<i>Rosielle & Scaggs (2008)</i>	Real-life events
<i>Rubin & Kontis (1983)</i>	Coin features
<i>Snyder et al., (2004)</i>	Computer keyboards
<i>Thorndike (1907)</i>	Familiar building
<i>Vendetti et al., (2013)</i>	The layout of elevator buttons
<i>Whatley et al., (2023)</i>	The Apple logo

Overall, the results from these previous studies suggest that regardless of continuous interaction with these objects, participants' memory accuracy was modest. The amount of information that people can retain from these objects is limited or small compared to other types of objects, while they remain overconfident about their ability to recall and recognize the objects (metamemory judgments).

Despite their continued presence and relevance in our daily environment, to our knowledge, only three studies have examined visual memory for brand visual logos,

(Blake et al., 2015; Iancu & Iancu, 2017; Whatley et al., 2023), and all three studies have focused exclusively on the Apple logo. Blake et al. (2015) assessed how undergraduate students drew and recognized the genuine Apple logo among modified versions acting as distractors. A single participant accurately drew the logo, and 47% chose the correct logo among distractors. In addition, participants showed significant overconfidence in their recall metamemory judgments despite their poor performance when asked before attempting to draw the logo. More recently, Iancu and Iancu (2017) replicated the study of Blake et al. (2015) in a different population (computer and social science specialists) and obtained similar results regarding memory performance and metacognitive judgments. Interestingly, variables such as sex, being a user of Apple devices or even having a very positive emotional attachment to the brand did not predict better performance on memory tasks. More recently, Whatley et al. (2023) tested recognition memory for the Apple logo under three different conditions: (1) after incidental exposure to an accurate or (2) an altered version of the logo or (3) no incidental encounter of the logo prior to the surprise test. The results showed that the incidental display of the altered logo disrupted the subsequent recognition of the correct logo compared to the other two conditions, although this effect diminished following the introduction of a 5-minute delay period between incidental encoding and testing. To explain the dissociation between the virtually unlimited visual memory capacity for repeatedly presented objects (Brady et al., 2008) and the poor memory for everyday settings reported in the previous literature, two different accounts have been proposed (see Castel et al., 2015 and Montoro & Ruiz, 2022, for reviews). The first one focuses on attentional mechanisms. According to this, when exposed to objects that do not need to be intentionally memorized due to the lack of functionality of the stimulus for the behavior, we cease to pay attention to them, that is, “inattentional amnesia” (Wolfe, 1999). A related process is “attentional saturation” (Bekerian & Baddeley, 1980), by which we stop paying attention to objects that are repeatedly presented without change or novelty. Supporting these attention-based accounts, some studies have found that participants improved their memory performance both when they had to study the items intentionally (Marmie & Healy, 2004) or when they were encouraged to attend to the object (Rinck, 1999).

The second account highlights memory-related factors derived from the reconstructive nature of memory processes (Bartlett, 1932) that lead to a generalized representation of the experienced events and a reduced amount of specific and distinctive memorized

details (Schank & Abelson, 1977). In this context, Nickerson and Adams (1979) found that memory representations of coins in their study often contained features from other non-presented coins. Moreover, in a study by Blake et al. (2017), the drawings of the Apple logo often exhibited features collected from real apples. In addition, Montoro and Ruiz (2022) found that participants' drawings of a famous monument contained intrusions from a prototypical overgeneralized schema for the concept of the "monumental gate" from Madrid.

In relation to memory-related factors, several previous studies (e.g., Blake et al., 2015; Iancu & Iancu, 2017; Montoro & Ruiz, 2022) showed poorer memory performance for everyday objects when memory was assessed using recall rather than recognition tasks, which is a common finding in memory studies. Despite the important differences in the efficiency of memory retrieval processes between recall and recognition tasks (e.g., Andrew & Bird, 1938; Diana et al., 2006), the advantage in the performance of recognition tasks in everyday settings may be attributed to a specific retrieval practice effect (see Montoro & Ruiz, 2022, for a similar account). Several studies have shown that learning improves when the memory test employs the same tasks used in previous retrieval attempts (see McDermott, 2021; Roediger & Karpicke, 2006, for a review). Similarly, it is also well-established that retrieval practice (i.e., the testing effect) produces greater learning and long-term retention (e.g., Roediger and Butler, 2011; see Rowland, 2014 for a review) than studying. Given that visual contact with logos is the most frequent way we interact with them in our daily lives, it seems reasonable that recognition tasks that resemble the way we encounter logos in natural environments (usually with visual contact) lead to higher memory performance with respect to recall tasks (Bergstein & Erdelyi, 2008).

Additionally, metamemory processes have been a focus of interest in this research context. The estimations of future performance within metamemory and confidence judgments made before and immediately after the participant gives their response, respectively, have been the mostly used in this type of task. Findings have shown a dissociation between poor performance in recall and recognition tasks of everyday settings and the overconfidence shown by participants, which has been replicated in several studies (e.g. Blake & Castel, 2019; Blake et al., 2017; Montoro & Ruiz, 2022). This pattern of results replicates the findings typically obtained in experimental studies using less naturalistic materials (see Dunlosky & Metcalfe, 2008, for a review). For example, Chua et al. (2012) found that the accuracy of one's memory and confidence

can diverge, with cognitive confidence influenced by both relevant (target retrieval experience) and irrelevant (cue fluency/familiarity) factors. Similarly, Pirmoradi and McKelvie (2015) observed this dissociation when they manipulated the participants' confidence in their study using false feedback; however, this manipulation did not affect memory performance. In this context, familiarity and availability (see Blake & Castel, 2019), ease of encoding (Hertzog et al., 2003), and retrieval fluency (Koriat & Ma'yan, 2005) seem to play important roles in this overconfidence bias. Consistent with basic research on metacognitive evaluation (e.g., Glenberg & Epstein, 1987; Koriat, 1993, 1995), it can be proposed that frequent exposure to naturalistic settings does not guarantee better memory performance for perceptual features of stimuli (at least for the case of recall/recognition tests); however, in contrast, it does increase confidence ratings, as metacognitive judgments are based on heuristic cues that make use of information sources not necessarily related to the target stimulus' visual appearance, such as familiarity with the common stimulus (due to frequent contact) or the accessibility of partial or spurious information (see Montoro & Ruiz, 2022, for a similar account).

This study extends prior work on everyday objects by examining memory for car logos for the first time and introducing a new task of naming logos to compare with recall and recognition tasks. Since their origins, commercial brands have made use of advertising to gain access to consumers; in particular, the development of logos has been one of the most important advances made by companies to identify brands and share their messages and values (Klein, 1985). In particular, the Spanish automotive industry accounts for 10% of the gross domestic product GDP of Spain, being the second main vehicle manufacturer in Europe and the eighth largest worldwide (Amadoz, 2019). Studying memory with respect to logos has both theoretical and practical implications. Logos are symbols that we interact with every day, making them suitable for researching the memory of everyday objects. Remarkably, the study of metacognition in the context of memory in everyday settings could provide relevant information about our own memories in naturalistic environments. Additionally, introducing different memory tasks (i.e., recall, recognition, and naming) to examine logo memory performance will allow us to further investigate the mechanisms involved in the incidental memory of everyday objects. Practically, the study of memory in natural contexts allows for a more complete and realistic approach to the functioning of memory outside the laboratory context (Castel et al., 2015), which could lead to

translational applications in fields such as marketing, advertising, and, particularly, branding.

Importantly, in addition to assessing recall and recognition (Study 1), Study 2 explored whether pictorial logos act as memory retrieval cues that allow easy access to a brand represented by a naming identification task. Finally, we assessed metamemory judgments in both studies, as well as other relevant variables and external predictors of performance, such as familiarity, car fondness, and years since obtaining the driving license.

We hypothesized that the best memory performance would be in the naming identification task (Study 2), followed by the recognition task, and the worst results would be in the recall task (Study 1).

Concerning metamemory judgments, we predicted that the participants would show an overconfidence bias when asked about their future performance in the recall/recognition task, which would be reduced after completing the drawing task. Metamemory judgments in the naming task will be less biased, given that we expect the logo to act as an adequate and effective cue for retrieving the car brand name.

Finally, variables such as familiarity, car fondness, or years since obtaining the driving license would have no or little effect on memory accuracy, according to previous literature.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to explore both the recall and recognition of car logos and their impact on identifying the brands they symbolize. This study extends the understanding of the roles of attention, memory, and metamemory processes in ecological contexts with objects that we daily have frequent contact with.

2. Study 1: Recall and recognition of memory logos

This study was conducted to explore how well participants remembered car logos, a particular type of visual object in everyday life with which we have frequent contact. Participants first performed a recall (drawing) task, followed by a recognition task, while metamemory judgments, familiarity, and other variables of interest were assessed.

2.1.Methods

2.1.1. Participants

In this study, 156 psychology students at the University of UNED (145 right-handed participants; 120 women; age: 18–64 years, mean age = 32 years) participated and received credit in exchange. The sample size was selected based on prior exploratory research and the anticipation of finding a medium effect size ($f^2 = 0.15$), in line with previous studies in this field. A power analysis was conducted with G*Power 3.1.9.2 ($f^2 = 0.15$, $\alpha = 0.05$, and $\beta = 0.80$) to estimate the minimum sample size required to detect a deviation of $R^2 = 0$ in a linear multiple regression analysis with a maximum of 4 different predictors. The results indicated that the minimum sample size required to achieve the target power was 85. Post hoc power analysis indicated that given our actual sample size, R^2 , and final number of predictors, we achieved a minimum power of $\beta = 0.99$. All the participants reported normal or correct-to-normal vision and signed an informed consent form before the study commenced. The experimental procedure was approved by the UNED's Ethics Committee and adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki.

2.1.2. Procedure and Materials

The entire study was conducted in a single session lasting approximately 45 minutes. The participants were tested in small groups in a large quiet room. Each participant received a pencil, eraser, and notebook containing several sheets of paper with instructions on the different tasks they should perform. After completing demographic questions (age, sex, handedness, nationality, and years of residence in Spain), the experimenters described each task as follows.

Recall task (drawing): Participants were asked to draw ten logos corresponding to well-known car brands (see Appendix 3 for the full instructions given to the participants) that were selected based on the ranking of cars manufactured (production volume) in Spain in 2019 (Amadoz 2019). From this ranking, we selected the top ten best-selling brands whose logos did not include the brand name. The experimenters emphasized to the participants that their artistic quality or drawing talent would not be assessed but that they were interested in the participants trying to draw the basic characteristics of the logos, such as the type of figure, prominent elements, and orientation. They had a maximum of five minutes to draw each logo. The drawings were later scored by three experimenters based on an individual rubric created for each logo. To ensure inter-judge reliability, all scores were assigned based on the agreement between the three judges. Prior to the rubric evaluation phase, the three judges conducted a training phase in which they jointly scored a subsample of the rubrics to ensure a common criterion. Each drawing score ranged from 0 to 5–8 points, and the final score for each participant in

each rubric was transformed to a common 0–100 scale to facilitate comparison between the recall level of the different brands and familiarity and confidence measures (see Appendix 1 for the rubric used for each logo). The rubric was designed to reflect the basic features of the original logo (type of figure, number of elements, orientation, relationship between the different elements of the object, and the presence or absence of different geometric shapes). The rubric did not assess the artistic quality of the drawings. Each basic feature of each logo was compared with individual participant's drawings and scored accordingly (See Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Example of three drawings made by three different participants when they were asked to draw the logo of the car brand "Peugeot" (that of 2019) with their corresponding scores. The figure below shows the correct logo and how the different features were scored according to the Peugeot Rubric on a 0–7 points scale.

Before and after the drawing task, participants were asked to rate how confident they were about the accuracy of their drawing using a 100-point scale (0 = “not at all” to 100 = “extremely confident”). Using the same scale, the participants were also asked about

their confidence in recognizing each logo presented among the potential distractors. Thus, the objective was to evaluate participants' confidence in their performance judgments before and after doing the recall (drawing) task. After giving their second confidence judgments, all the participants performed the recognition task.

Recognition Task: Participants were asked to rank six alternative versions of each logo (the correct logo and five modified versions). The modified logos were created by changing the simple features of the original logo (e.g., orientation, number of elements, relationship between elements, and presence or absence of geometric shapes) (see Figure 2). In line with Montoro and Ruiz (2022), the participants had to rank logos on a “scale of reality” from “the most similar or realistic version” to “the less similar or less realistic version” by allotting numbers from 1 to 6, respectively. The response was forced, and the numbers could not be repeated.

Afterwards, participants completed a short questionnaire about their degree of car fondness using a 100-point scale, whether they had a driving license (if so, for how long), and their current and past car brands. Finally, the participants were asked about their familiarity with 15 car logos (the 10 evaluated in the previous tasks were intermixed with 5 new ones) on a 100-point scale (0 = “not at all” to 100 = “extremely familiar”).

Figure 2.

Target logos and distractors employed in the recognition task.

Note: Distractors were created by modifying the orientation, number, and type of intrinsic or extrinsic elements to the stimuli and geometric shapes. The correct version of each car logo is circled in green.

To ensure that participants understood what to do in each task, the "Apple logo" was used as an example to estimate confidence in recall (assessment of their own ability to draw the logos) and recognition (ability to discriminate between the original logo when presented intermixed with its altered versions) as well as familiarity (the frequency of contact with the logo).

2.2. Results

2.2.1. Recall/recognition performance and metamemory judgments

Preliminary comparisons

Figures 3 and 4 display the actual performance, confidence in performance judgments (before and after the task), familiarity judgments in drawing (recall), and recognition tasks for each car brand employed in Study 1, respectively.

The one-sample t-tests conducted on the drawing performance (measured as the mean score obtained by each participant in drawing each brand logo, as described in the *Procedure and Materials* section) for each car brand included in the study indicated that drawing performance was above zero for all car brands (all $p < 0.01$). Overall, the drawing performance reached $M = 49.08$ (Standard Deviation (SD) = 22.38). The metamemory judgments regarding drawing performance were $M = 60.74$ (SD = 23.66) and $M = 55.83$ (SD = 23.04) for judgments made before and after the recall task, respectively. Paired samples t-tests performed between confidence judgments and actual performance indicated statistically significant overconfidence in the confidence judgments both before [$t(153) = 8.29, p < 0.001, d = 0.50$] and after [$t(155) = 6.26, p < 0.001, d = 0.30$] the task, which seemed to decrease after the completion of the task (11.66% and 6.75% overconfidence, respectively).

Figure 3.

Drawing (recall) performance, metamemory (confidence), and familiarity judgments for each car brand included in the study.

Drawing (recall) performance (% correct), metamemory (confidence before/after) judgments (%), and familiarity judgments (%) for each car brand included in the study. The error bars represent 1 SEM.

One-sample Z-tests were conducted on recognition performance (hit proportion). A hit consisted of ranking the original logo as first in the recognition test for each car brand, showing that performance in the recognition task was above chance level (16,67%) for all brands included in the study (all p s < 0.01; except Peugeot $p = 0.09$). Overall, the recognition performance was $M = 74.36$ ($SD = 18.60$). The metamemory judgments regarding recognition performance reached $M = 77.86$ ($SD = 19.51$) and $M = 75.77$ ($SD = 22,17$), respectively, for judgments made before and after the recognition task (3.5% and 1.4% overconfidence, respectively). However, paired t-tests showed that confidence in recognition judgments did not significantly differ from the actual performance in recognition before [$t_{\text{before}}(1, 152) = 1.83, p = 0.069$] or after [$t_{\text{after}}(1, 154) = 0.71, p = 0.481$] the task.

Figure 4.

Memory (recognition) performance, metamemory (confidence), and familiarity judgments for each car brand were included in the study.

Memory (recognition) performance (% correct), metamemory (confidence before/after) judgments (%), and familiarity judgments (%) for each car brand included in the study. The error bars represent 1 SEM. The dashed line indicates the chance level for recognition performance (16.66%).

Global comparisons

To further investigate the adjustment of metamemory judgments regarding performance in recall and recognition tasks, we performed a 2×2 repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the within-subjects factor *evaluation moment* (before task, after task) and *task* (recall, recognition) on the accuracy of the judgments. This *confidence adjustment* was computed by subtracting the actual performance in each task from the confidence judgments (confidence% – accuracy%) for each evaluation moment and task, which is a calibration measure usually employed in metamemory research to analyze the global adjustment of metamemory judgments (Cauvin et al., 219). The results revealed a main effect of task $F(1, 151) = 14.501, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.09, \beta = 0.97$, indicating a poorer adjustment (greater overconfidence) in the recall task ($M = 9.02$) compared to recognition ($M = 2.17\%$). The main effect of evaluation moment also

reached statistical significance $F(1, 151) = 12.52, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.08, \beta = 0.94$, showing an increase in metamemory adjustment when confidence judgments were performed after completing the task ($M_{\text{before}} = 7.23\%$; $M_{\text{after}} = 3.96\%$). Finally, the statistically significant first-order interaction between evaluation moment and task $F(1, 151) = 7.44, p = 0.007, \eta^2 = 0.05, \beta = 0.77$ qualifies the main effects found in the analysis. Post hoc pairwise comparisons (Bonferroni corrected) showed that the adjustment of confidence in recall judgments improved after performing the task from 11.66% to 6.75% ($p < 0.001$), but the adjustment of confidence in recognition judgments did not change. Figure 5 summarizes the ANOVA results.

Figure 5.

Overconfidence as a function of the task performed.

Percentage of overconfidence (confidence – actual performance) before and after each task in Study 1 (recognition and recall (drawing)). The error bars represent 1 SEM.

2.2.2. Predictors of recall and recognition performance

The metamemory confidence judgments regarding recall performance reached values higher than the actual performance on the recall task, particularly when these judgments were made before the task (overconfidence). However, Pearson's correlation analyses showed a significant correlation between recall confidence and performance, both

before and after completing the task ($r = 0.721$ and $r = 0.824$, respectively; all $ps < 0.001$). Similar positive significant correlations with recall performance were found for familiarity judgments ($r = 0.445$, $p < 0.001$) and car fondness ($r = 0.427$, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 6 shows a summary of the correlations among the variables collected in Study 1.

Figure 6.

Correlation matrix in Study 1

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

To analyze these variables as predictors of recall performance, a hierarchical multiple linear regression analysis was performed, introducing these factors according to their correlation with recall performance. The model including confidence in recall before the task ($R^2_{\text{change}} = 0.514$, $p < 0.001$), familiarity ($R^2_{\text{change}} = 0.023$, $p = 0.01$), and car

fondness ($R^2_{\text{change}} = 0.014, p = 0.038$) as predictors, explained 54% of the variance (adjusted $R^2 = 0.542$). Table 2 presents a summary of the regression model for the recall performance.

Table 2.

Linear model of predictors of recall performance.

	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	<i>p</i>
Constant	4.493	3.893	-	0.250
Confidence	0.575	0.063	0.605	<0.001
Familiarity	0.134	0.072	0.125	0.065
Car fondness	0.119	0.057	0.138	0.038

B: unstandardized coefficients; *SE B*: standard error of B; β : standardized coefficients

Confidence judgments for recognition performance were not significant for over- or under-confidence. Pearson's correlation analysis revealed significant correlations between confidence in recognition before and after completing the task and recognition performance ($r = 0.338$ and $r = 0.405$, respectively; all $ps < 0.001$). Familiarity judgments ($r = 0.205, p = 0.008$) and car fondness ($r = 0.212, p = 0.006$) also showed significant positive correlations with recognition performance¹.

As with the recall task, to analyze the role of these variables in predicting recognition performance, a hierarchical multiple linear regression analysis was conducted, including confidence judgments (before the task), familiarity, and car fondness as predictor variables. The model including confidence in recognition before the task explained 11% of the variance (adjusted $R^2 = 0.113$). As predictors, neither the addition of familiarity ($R^2_{\text{change}} = 0.006, p = 0.320$) nor car fondness ($R^2_{\text{change}} = 0.004, p = 0.440$) significantly improved the model predictions. Table 3 presents a summary of the regression models for the recognition performance.

¹ It should be noted that according to the magnitude of the correlation between the performance on the drawing and the recognition tasks (see figure 6), performance on the drawing task should have been included as a predictor in the regression model of recognition performance. However, given the high correlation between the main predictor of the model (confidence in recognition before the task) and the performance on the drawing task, we decided not to include it to avoid the high collinearity between two different predictors in the regression model. Since our main interest was to investigate the predictive capacity of confidence judgments on subsequent performance, we kept confidence in recognition, and exclude performance on the drawing task as a predictor.

Table 3.

Linear model of predictors of recognition performance.

	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	<i>p</i>
Constant	49.355	6.091	-	<0.001
Confidence	0.275	0.080	0.300	<0.001
Familiarity	0.050	0.077	0.059	0.519
Car fondness	0.049	0.063	0.071	0.440

B: unstandardized coefficients; *SE B*: standard error of B; β : standardized coefficients.

Both recall and recognition memory for logos showed great variability between brands, even though the participants' global performance on the recall task was worse (49%) than that on the recognition task (74%). Confidence in recall and recognition were reliable predictors of task performance. However, participants' overconfidence occurred only in the drawing task (before and after performing the task, although they corrected their estimates after performing the task) but not in the recognition task, where they matched their confidence judgments to their performance. Interestingly, a high recognition performance did not always correspond to a high recall performance, and vice versa. For example, some brands, such as “Nissan,” showed high recognition performance, whereas their recall levels remained very low. In contrast, brands such as “Peugeot” achieved high recall performance, while their recognition rates were lower. To explore whether participants could improve their accuracy when confronted with situations resembling real-life interactions with brand logos, we conducted a new study with a new group of participants, designed to examine whether they would more easily identify car logos when asked to write the name of the brand in the presence of its logo.

3. Study 2: Naming Memory Logos

3.1. Methods

3.1.1. Participants

A new sample of 119 psychology students at the UNED University (116 were right-handed; 94 women; age: 19–63 years; mean age = 32.85 years) participated in the second study and received credit in exchange. The sample size was selected based on prior exploratory research and the anticipation of finding a medium effect size, in line with previous studies in this field. As in Study 1, a power analysis was conducted with G*Power 3.1.9.2 ($f^2 = 0.15$, $\alpha = 0.05$, and $\beta = 0.80$) to estimate the minimum sample

size required to detect a deviation of $R^2 = 0$ in a linear multiple regression analysis with a maximum of 4 different predictors. The results indicated that the minimum sample size required to achieve the target power was 85. Post hoc power analysis indicated that given the actual sample size of Study 2, R^2 and the final number of predictors, we achieved a power of $\beta = 1.00$. All the participants reported normal or correct-to-normal vision and signed an informed consent form before the study commenced. The experimental procedure was approved by the UNED's Ethics Committee and adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki.

3.1.2. Procedure and Materials

The participants were tested in small groups in a large quiet room at the Faculty of Psychology (UNED). The single session lasted approximately 30 minutes (see Appendix 4 for the full instructions given to the participants).

The participants were given a notebook containing several sheets of paper, with instructions for the different tasks they had to perform in the experimental session and the order in which they should complete them. After filling in the same demographic data as in Study 1 (age, sex, handedness, nationality, and years of residence in Spain), the experimenters described the experimental procedure to the participants as follows.

Naming Task: Participants were instructed to write down the name of twenty-four brand logos, and seven were selected from those employed in Study 1 (the other three logos used in Study 1 were removed as they included letters in the logo that could provide relevant clues for naming the brand). Five were new car logos, and twelve were logos for non-car commercial brands used as *fillers* to prevent participants from suspecting that the study focused exclusively on car brand logos and, therefore, from deploying logo name guessing strategies by simply saying *random* car brand names retrieved from memory (see Appendix 2). Participants also rated their confidence in their answers on a 100-point scale (0 = "not at all" to 100 = "extremely confident"). Unlike in Study 1, confidence judgments in Study 2 were collected simultaneously with the naming task. After completing the naming task, participants filled in a short questionnaire about their degree of car fondness, whether they had a driving license (if so, for how long), and the brands of their current and past cars. Finally, participants were asked about their familiarity with all the previously named logos using a 100-point scale (0 = "not at all" to 100 = "extremely familiar").

3.2. Results

3.2.1. Naming performance and metamemory judgments

Figure 7 shows the mean actual performance, confidence in performance judgments, and familiarity judgments in the naming task for each of the seven car brands employed in Study 2 and shared with Study 1. The data from the 12 non-car brand logos were not included in the statistical analyses because they were merely included as *fillers* with an experimental control motivation (for more information, see the *Procedure and Materials* section).

The one-sample Z-tests conducted on naming performance for each car brand included in the study indicated that recall performance was above zero for all brands (all *ps* <0.01). Overall, the naming performance reached $M = 92.11$ ($SD = 16.56$). The confidence judgments regarding naming performance were $M = 91.94$ ($SD = 13.59$), showing a near-perfect calibration with no significant under- or overconfidence.

Figure 7.

Memory (naming) performance, metamemory (confidence), and familiarity judgments for each of the car brands under study.

Memory (naming) performance (% correct), metamemory judgments (%), and familiarity judgments (%) for each car brand included in the study. The error bars represent 1 SEM.

3.2.2. Predictors of naming performance

Confidence judgments for naming performance did not show significant over- or under-confidence. Pearson's correlation analysis showed a significant correlation between confidence in naming and naming performance ($r = 0.852, p < 0.001$). Car fondness ($r = 0.484, p < 0.001$), familiarity ($r = 0.372, p < 0.001$) and years of residence ($r = 0.286, p < 0.01$) also showed a significant positive correlation with naming performance. Figure 8 shows a summary of the correlations among the variables collected in Study 2.

Figure 8. Correlation matrix for Study 2

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Finally, to analyze the role of these variables in predicting naming performance, hierarchical multiple linear regression analysis was conducted, including confidence judgments, car fondness, familiarity, and years of residence as predictor variables. The model including confidence in naming as the only predictor explained 74,8% of the variance (adjusted $R^2 = 0.748$). The addition of car fondness ($R^2_{\text{change}} = 0.000, p = 0.859$), familiarity ($R^2_{\text{change}} = 0.001, p = 0.663$) and years of residence ($R^2_{\text{change}} = 0.00, p = 0.874$) as predictors did not significantly improve the model predictions. Table 4 summarizes the regression model for the naming performance.

Table 4.

Linear model of predictors of naming performance.

	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	β	<i>p</i>
Constant	-6.311	6.330	-	0.321
Confidence	1.063	0.072	0.868	<0.001
Car fondness	-0.009	0.036	-0.014	0.805
Familiarity	0.016	0.036	0.026	0.648
Years of residence	-0.012	0.074	-0.009	0.874

B: unstandardized coefficients; *SE B*: standard error of B; β : standardized coefficients.

Combined analysis of Studies 1 and 2. A combined analysis of Studies 1 (drawing and recognition) and (naming) 2, including the seven car brands shared in both studies, was conducted to explore the differences and confidence judgments in performance and the adjustment of the confidence judgments between the tasks in both studies. To this end, we conducted two different one-way independent measures multivariate ANOVA (MANOVA) with the factor *task* (drawing vs. naming and recognition vs. naming) as the between-subjects variable and performance (accuracy%), confidence in performance (%), and confidence adjustment (confidence% – accuracy%) as dependent variables. The first MANOVA compared the drawing and naming tasks. The multivariate results based on Wilk’s statistic showed a significant main effect of the task $\Lambda = 0.581$ $F(2, 249) = 89.65, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.419, \beta = 1.00$. Follow-up univariate analyses indicated that significant differences between drawing and naming tasks emerged for all the dependent variables: performance $F(1, 250) = 175.60, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.413, \beta = 1.00$, confidence in performance $F(1, 250) = 145.11, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.367, \beta = 1.00$, and confidence adjustment $F(1, 250) = 10.09, p = 0.002, \eta^2 = 0.039, \beta = 0.886$. The second MANOVA compared the recognition and naming tasks. The multivariate results based on Wilk’s statistic showed a significant main effect of the task $\Lambda = 0.744$ $F(2, 249) = 42.86, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.256, \beta = 1.00$. Follow-up univariate analyses indicated that significant differences between recognition and naming tasks emerged for the three dependent variables analyzed: performance $F(1, 250) = 85.05, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.254, \beta = 1.00$, confidence in performance $F(1, 250) = 29.54, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.106, \beta = 1.00$, and confidence adjustment $F(1, 250) = 14.35, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.054, \beta = 0.96$. An overview of the results is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9.

Memory performance, confidence judgments, and overconfidence as a function of the task performed in Studies 1 and 2.

Memory performance (% correct), confidence judgments (%), and overconfidence (confidence – actual performance) in the recall (drawing), recognition, and naming tasks (Studies 1 and 2). The error bars represent 1 SEM.

Not surprisingly, participants almost perfectly named the brands of the seven car logos used in Study 2 (92%). Furthermore, a near-perfect correlation existed between task confidence (91%) and accuracy, with naming confidence being the best predictor of task accuracy (similar to recall and recognition confidence in Study 1). A detailed comparison between these three tasks is presented in the following section.

The data supporting the findings of this study are openly available in [Open Science Framework] at [https://osf.io/6fx5t/?view_only=296cd7aca3cd4bb3bdf10d9312753458]

4. General Discussion

One of the goals of automotive manufacturers is to design iconic representations of their brands that allow us to identify them quickly and accurately. However, as previous research has shown, even if specifically designed to be remembered, frequent interactions with a specific stimulus do not guarantee a detailed future memory trace. The results obtained in relation to memory performance and metacognitive judgments are discussed below.

4.1. Memory performance

The results of Study 1 agreed with our initial assumptions. Specifically, we found that the participants' memory performance (especially in the drawing task) was relatively modest, as other studies with logos showed previously (Blake et al. 2015; Iancu & Iancu, 2017). This poor performance is congruent with previous literature, stressing that incidental encoding generates a less detailed representation in long-term memory than intentional encoding (e.g., Draschkow et al., 2018; Marmie & Healy, 2004; Rinck, 1999). For example, Marmie and Healy (2004) found higher levels of recall for an unfamiliar coin's features after a brief intentional study. In addition, Rinck (1999) improved learning and retention of the numerical layouts of calculators and telephone keypads by directing people's attention toward them. In these studies, the locus of memory failure appeared to be in the encoding phase rather than in the retrieval phase. Interestingly, impairment due to incidental (shallow) encoding in a later memory test seemed to affect free and cued recall tests more than recognition tests (Eagle & Leiter, 1964; Wagnon et al., 2019).

The performance in the naming task (Study 2) was superior to that of recall and recognition (Study 1). In this study, the main change with respect to Study 1 was the task performed by the participants and, therefore, the specific retrieval conditions. In Study 2, the participants had to write down the brand name when presented with a brand logo. In this context, the car logo may act as an effective retrieval cue that can automatically activate the memory trace for the brand (Anderson, 2020), a situation very similar to the ones in which we incidentally encounter and interact with logos in natural environments. Considering this, the increased performance in the naming task could be explained by the beneficial effect of retrieval practice on memory performance, in which retrieving the previously studied information fosters long-term retention (see Rowland, 2014 for a review). Applied to the current context, most of the time when we encounter logos in our environment, they are presented alone, requiring us to retrieve the brand name (an example of a retrieval practice that would lead to better memory for

the brand name in the presence of the logo as a cue). Accordingly, the best explanation for the higher accuracy in the naming task could be that this task resembles the way observers contact and practice the retrieval of brands associated with logos in a daily context.

This direct interaction in natural contexts with the logos and their names could also explain why the performance in the recognition task (in which participants were required to rank different versions of the same logo) was superior to that in the recall task (in which the process was reversed, and the brand name acted as a retrieval key for the logo). Specifically, the recognition task employed here requires looking for differences among similar versions of the same logo, which involves more analytical processing focused on the stimulus features (e.g., the number of circles in the Audi logo), rather than familiarity or fluency-based processing. According to the dual account of recognition memory (Yonelinas, 2001), it depends on two underlying components, recollection and familiarity, which are based on different processes. Recollection is a threshold process by which qualitative information about a memorized object is retrieved. Familiarity, however, is based on a classical signal-detection process, whereby items that exceed a given familiarity level are accepted as correct. Responses based on recollection processes resulted in higher levels of confidence and performance in metacognitive judgments and recognition tasks, respectively, relative to responses based on familiarity processes. The recognition task required the participants to analytically process the characteristics of each version of the logo, and the higher performance level is normal as this more analytical processing would depend more on the *recollection* component of recognition rather than on the *familiarity-based* component, (Montoro & Ruiz, 2022; Yonelinas, 2001).

The better memory performances for naming results, followed by recognition and drawing (recall) are not surprising given that car logos are not designed to be remembered in detail (which meets the requirements of a drawing/recall task) but rather to allow us to retrieve the name of the brand they represent (which matches the requirements of a naming task) and make it distinguishable from other similar brands (which corresponds to a recognition task). In other words, logos are designed as valid and automatic cues that make the brand name readily available, allowing us to distinguish it from other brands. It is precisely because of this reason that brand counterfeiters benefit from designing logos that are very similar in their overall form (altering some specific details such as removing graphical information and modifying

the typeface) but are not identical to the original brand. As most of the key features of counterfeit logos are common to those of the original brand, they are easily distinguishable from other brands but are very difficult to discern from the original brand. For example, in recent studies on commercial brands (Pathak et al., 2019a, b; Perea et al., 2021), the authors found that the logos used by companies were highly vulnerable to counterfeiting through misspelled words that the customers did not notice.

4.2. Metacognitive judgments

In all the tasks, metamemory judgments regarding recall, recognition, and naming were the best predictors of memory performance. Interestingly, metamemory judgments were quite accurate in the recognition task, and we found a clear effect of overconfidence only in the recall task, which was reduced after the task was performed (Study 1). Moreover, in the naming task (Study 2), participants perfectly matched their confidence judgments and performance, an expected result given that the logo is a powerful retrieval cue for the brand name, as both are often presented together in real life (see Blake et al., 2015; Iancu & Iancu, 2017; Montoro & Ruiz, 2022 for similar results). These results agree with a heuristic account of metamemory processes, according to which metamemory judgments are not based on direct access to the memory trace and its strength but on the information available at the time the judgment is made (Koriat, 2008) and the ease of processing the items to be remembered (Dunlosky & Metcalfe, 2008). Car logos are easily processed because they have little visual complexity (Janiszewski & Meyvis, 2001). Moreover, the logos that we frequently see make it easier for us to create a mental image, even if it is vague and lacking in detail, which typically leads to a non-predictive increase in the magnitude of confidence judgments (Kelley & Lindsay, 1993). In addition, and related to the contact frequency and accessibility of the logos, the availability heuristic (Tversky & Kahneman, 1973) could explain why people evaluate the items to be remembered as highly available when they repeatedly interact with them. Another factor that could have affected confidence judgments in our study was the accessibility of information related to the car brand (other than the logo itself), such as car models, dealerships, or races. When we search our memory for a requested logo, these pieces of information come to mind, enhancing the feeling of knowing and, ultimately, the magnitude of the confidence judgments. Unfortunately, this information is independent of the perceptual features of the logo and is not useful for improving the performance in drawing and recognition tasks (see Montoro & Ruiz, 2022, p. 778, for a similar account). In support of this explanation,

experimental research has found that the retrieval of contextual non-target information can spuriously raise metamemory judgments based on the target information (Glenberg & Epstein, 1987; Koriat, 1993, 1995).

Although all the aforementioned factors would also play an important role in the naming task (which may, therefore, give rise to the same overconfidence phenomenon), a ceiling effect may exist because participants in the naming task have near-perfect accuracy. Therefore, in our study, it was not possible to discern whether near-perfect confidence judgments in the naming task actually reflected good metamemory adjustment of the participants.

4.3. Limitations and future research directions

This study has some limitations. One of the most important factors was the difference in performance between the logos in Study 1. A possible explanation is the absence of matching in terms of the visual complexity of the images used in the study (e.g., Anderson & Leonard, 1958; Chai, 2010; Nguyen & McDaniel, 2015; Kayaert & Wagemans, 2009). Future studies should control for this dimension of stimuli.

Similarly, the distractors in the recognition task were not formally matched in terms of the degree to which they differed from the original logo, a feature that could affect recognition performance and confidence judgments.

Finally, another limitation pertains to the sample, consisting mostly of psychology students and predominantly female participants.

4.4. Summing up and conclusions

To our knowledge, this is the first study to employ car logos to explore memory performance and metamemory judgments in the context of everyday environments.

Overall, our memory for everyday objects is fallible. The literature review suggests that mechanisms related to attention and memory may account for the impoverished memory of car logos. Unlike the recall or recognition memory tasks, the naming task was performed almost perfectly by the participants. The mechanisms associated with memory retrieval processes may underlie this excellent performance. This research has important implications from not only a theoretical perspective but also an applied perspective in the context of marketing studies.

1. References

- Amadoz, S. (2019, July 11th). Las 20 marcas de coches que más circulan por las carreteras de España. El País. <https://motor.elpais.com/actualidad/marcas-que-mas-circulan/>
- Anderson, M.C. (2020). *Retrieval*. In A. Baddeley, M.W. Eysenck & M.C. Anderson (Eds.), *Memory* (2nd ed., pp. 233-271). Routledge. Taylor & Francis Group. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429449642>
- Anderson, N. S. & Leonard, J. A. (1958). The recognition, naming, and reconstruction of visual figures as a function of contour redundancy. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, *56*, 262–270, <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0044893>
- Andrew, D. M., & Bird, C. (1938). A comparison of two new-type questions: recall and recognition. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *29*(3), 175–193. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0062394>
- Bartlett, F. C. (1932). *Remembering: A study in experimental and social psychology*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bekarian, D. A., & Baddeley, A. D. (1980). Saturation advertising and the repetition effect. *Journal of Verbal Learning & Verbal Behavior*, *19*(1), 17–25. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-5371\(80\)90476-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-5371(80)90476-4)
- Bergstein, J., & Erdelyi, M. (2008). Recognition hypermnesia: how to get it. *Memory*, *16* (7), 689-702. doi: DOI:10.1080/09658210802169095
- Blake, A.B., & Castel, A.D. (2015). Metamemory. In S.K. Whitbourne (Ed.) *The encyclopedia of adulthood and aging* (pp. 1-5). John Wiley & Sons, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118521373.wbeaa043>
- Blake, A.B., & Castel, A.D. (2019). Memory and availability-biases metacognitive illusions for flags of varying familiarity. *Memory & Cognition*, *47*, 365-382. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13421-018-0872-y>
- Blake, A.B., Nazarian, M., & Castel, A.D. (2015). The Apple of the mind's eye: Everyday attention, metamemory, and reconstructive memory for the Apple logo. *The Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*, *68* (5), 858-865. [10.1080/17470218.2014.1002798](https://doi.org/10.1080/17470218.2014.1002798)
- Brady, T.F., Konkle, T., Alvarez, G. A., & Oliva, A. (2008). Visual long-term memory has a massive storage capacity for object details. *PNAS Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *105*(38), 14325–14329. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0803390105>

- Castel, A.D., Nazarian, M., & Blake, A.B. (2015). Attention and Incidental Memory in Everyday Settings. In J.M. Fawcett, E.F. Risko, & A. Kingstone (Eds.), *The handbook of attention* (pp. 463-483). MIT Press.
- Castel, A. D., Vendetti, M., & Holyoak, K. J. (2012). Fire drill: Inattentive blindness and amnesia for the location of fire extinguishers. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, *74*(7), 1391–1396. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-012-0355-3>
- Cauvin, S., Moulin, C., Souchay, C., Kliegel, M. & Schnitzspahn, K.M. (2019) Prospective Memory Predictions in Aging: Increased Overconfidence in Older Adults, *Experimental Aging Research*, *45*:5, 436-459, DOI: 10.1080/0361073X.2019.1664471
- Chai, X.J. (2010). Scene complexity: Influence on perception, memory, and development in the medial temporal lobe. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, *4*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2010.00021>
- Chua, E. F., Hannula, D. E., & Ranganath, C. (2012). Distinguishing highly confident accurate and inaccurate memory: insights about relevant and irrelevant influences on memory confidence. *Memory* *20*(1), 48–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09658211.2011.633919>
- Diana, R.A., Reder, L.M., Arndt, J. *et al.* Models of recognition: A review of arguments in favor of a dual-process account (2006). *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, *13*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03193807>
- Draschkow, D., Reinecke, S., Cunningham, C.A., Vö, L.-H.M. (2018). The lower bounds of massive memory: Investigating memory for object details in incidental encoding. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1747021818783722>
- Dunlosky, J., & Metcalfe, J. (2008). *Metacognition*. Sage Publications.
- Eagle, M., & Leiter, E. (1964). Recall and recognition in intentional and incidental learning. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, *68*(1), 58–63. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0044655>
- Ebbinghaus, H. (1964). *Memory* (Trans. H. A. Ruger and C. E. Bussenius). New York: Dover (Original work published 1885).
- French, C.C., & Richards, A. (1993). Clock*this!: An everyday example of a schema-driven error in memory. *British Journal of Psychology*, *84*(2), 249-253. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8295.1993.tb02477.x>

- Glenberg, A. M., & Epstein, W. (1987). Inexpert calibration of comprehension. *Memory & Cognition*, *15*, 84–93. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03197714>
- Hargis, M.B., McGillivray, S., & Castel, A.D. (2018). Memory for textbook covers: When and why we remember a book by its cover. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, *32*, 39-46.
- Hertzog, C., Dunlosky, J., Robinson, A.E., & Kider, D.P. (2003). Encoding fluency is a cue used for judgments about learning. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory and Cognition*, *20* (1), 22-34. DOI: [10.1037//0278-7393.29.1.22](https://doi.org/10.1037//0278-7393.29.1.22)
- Iancu, I., & Iancu, B. (2017). Recall and Recognition on Minimalism. A Replication of the Case Study on the Apple Logo. *KOME*, *5* (2), 57-70.
- Janiszewski, C., & Meyvis, T. (2001). Effects of brand logo complexity, repetition, and spacing on processing fluency and judgment. *Journal of Consumer Research*, *28*(1), 18–32. <https://doi.org/10.1086/321945>
- Jones, G.V. (1990). Misremembering a common object: When left is not right. *Memory & Cognition*, *18* (2), 174-182.
<https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.3758/BF03197093.pdf>
- Jones, G.V., & Martin, M. (1992). Misremembering a familiar object: Mnemonic illusion, not drawing bias. *Memory & Cognition*, *20*(2), 211-213.
- Kayaert, G., & Wagemans, J. (2009). Delayed shape matching benefits from simplicity and symmetry. *Visual Research*, *49*, 708-717. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.visres.2009.01.002>
- Kelley, C. M., & Lindsay, D. S. (1993). Remembering mistaken for knowing: Ease of retrieval as a basis for confidence in answers to general knowledge questions. *Journal of Memory and Language*, *32*(1), 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmla.1993.1001>
- Klein, S. (1985). The role of Marketing in economic development. *Quarterly Journal of Business and Economics*, *24* (4), 54-69. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40472834>
- Koriat, A. (1993). How do we know that we know? The accessibility model of the feeling of knowing. *Psychological Review*, *100*(4), 609–639.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.100.4.609>
- Koriat, A. (1995). Dissociating knowing and the feeling of knowing: Further evidence for the accessibility model. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, *124*(3), 311–333. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.124.3.311>

- Koriat, A. (2008). Easy comes, easy goes? The link between learning and remembering and its exploitation in metacognition. *Memory & Cognition*, *36*, 416–428.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/MC.36.2.416>
- Koriat, A., & Ma'ayan, H. (2005). The effects of encoding fluency and retrieval fluency on judgments of learning. *Journal of Memory and Language*, *52*(4), 478-492.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jml.2005.01.001>
- Liu, X., Crump, M. J. C., & Logan, G. D. (2010). Do you know where your fingers have been? Explicit knowledge of the spatial layout of the keyboard in skilled typists. *Memory & Cognition*, *38*, 474–484. doi:10.3758/MC.38.4.474
- McDermott, K. (2021). Practicing retrieval facilitates learning. *Annual Review of Psychology*, *72*, 609–633. doi: 10.1146/annurev-psych-010419-051019
- Mandler, J. & Ritchey, G. (1977). Long-term memory for pictures. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Learning and Memory*, *3*, 386-396.
 10.1037/0278-7393.3.4.386
- Marmie, W.R., & Healy, A.F. (2004). Memory for common objects: Brief intentional study is sufficient to overcome poor recall of UZ coin features. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, *18*, 121-123. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.994>
- Martin, M., & Jones, G.V. (1998). Generalizing everyday memory: Signs and handedness. *Memory & Cognition*, *26*, 193-200.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03201132>
- Misra, P., Marconi, A., Peterson, M., & Kreiman, G. (2018). Minimal memory for details in real life events. *Scientific Reports*, *8*: 16701. doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-33792-2.
- Montoro, P. R., & Ruiz, M. (2022). Incidental visual memory and metamemory for a famous monument. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, *84*(3), 771–780. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-022-02472-9>
- Murphy, D.H., & Castel, A.D. (2021). Tall towers: Schemas and illusions when perceiving and remembering a familiar building. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, *35*, 1236-1246. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.3855>
- Nguyen, K., & McDaniel, M.A. (2015). The picture complexity effect: another list composition paradox. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory and Cognition*, *41*, 1026–1037. doi: 10.1037/xlm0000071
- Nickerson, R.S., & Adams, M.J. (1979). Long-term memory for a common object. *Cognitive Psychology*, *11*, 287-307.

- Palumbo, R., Di Domenico, A., Fairfield, B. *et al.* (2021). When twice is better than once: increased liking of repeated items influences memory in younger and older adults. *BMC Psychology*, *9*, 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-021-00531-8>
- Park, C.W., & Eisingerich, A.B., & Park, J.W. (2013). *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, *23*, 229–248. [10.1016/j.jcps.2013.01.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcps.2013.01.002).
- Pathak, A., Velasco, C. & Calvert, G.A. (2019a). Identifying counterfeit brand logos: on the importance of the first and last letters of a logotype. *European Journal of Marketing*, *53* (10), 2109-2125. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-09-2017-0586>
- Perea, M., Baciero, A., Rocabado, F., & Marcet, A. (2021). Does the cowl make the monk? Detecting counterfeits in brand names versus logos. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, *28*, 969–977. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-020-01863-z>
- Pirmoradi, M., & McKelvie, S. (2015). Feedback, confidence, and false recall in the DRMRS procedure. *Current Psychology*, *34*(2), 248–267. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-014-9255-0>
- Rinck, M. (1999). Memory for everyday objects: Where are the digits on numerical keypads? *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, *13*(4), 329–350. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-0720\(199908\)13:4<329::AID-ACP583>3.0.CO;2-3](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-0720(199908)13:4<329::AID-ACP583>3.0.CO;2-3)
- Roediger, H. L. III, & Butler, A. C. (2011). The critical role of retrieval practice in long-term retention. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *15*(1), 20–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2010.09.003>
- Roediger, H. L., & Karpicke, J. D. (2006a). Test-enhanced learning: taking memory tests improves long-term memory. *Psychological Science*, *17*, 249–255. doi: [10.1111/j.1467-9280.2006.01693.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.2006.01693.x)
- Rosielle, L.J., & Scaggs, J.W. (2008). What if they knocked down the library and nobody noticed? The failure to detect large changes to familiar scenes. *Memory*, *16* (2), 115-124. DOI:[10.1080/09658210701787765](https://doi.org/10.1080/09658210701787765)
- Rowland, C. A. (2014). The effect of testing versus re-study on retention: A meta-analytic review of the testing effect. *Psychological Bulletin*, *140*(6), 1432–1463. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0037559>
- Rubin, D.C., & Kontis, T.C. (1983). A schema for common cents. *Memory & Cognition*, *11*, 335-341. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03202446>
- Schank, R.C., & Abelson, R. (1977). *Scripts, plans, goals and understanding*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.

- Snyder, K.M., Ashitaka, YI, Shimada, H., Ulrich, J.E., & Logan, G.D. (2014). What skilled typists don't know about the QWERTY key-board. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, 76, 162-171. DOI:[10.3758/s13414-013-0548-4](https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-013-0548-4)
- Thorndike, E.L. (1907). On the function of visual images. *The Journal of Philosophy, Psychology and Scientific Methods*, 4, 324-327.
- Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D. (1973). Availability: A heuristic for judging frequency and probability. *Cognitive Psychology*, 5(2), 207–232. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285\(73\)90033-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285(73)90033-9)
- Vendetti, M., Castel, A.D., & Holyoak, K.J. (2013). The floor effect: Impoverished spatial memory for elevator buttons). *Attention, Perception & Psychophysics*, 75, 636-643. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-012-0355-3>
- Wagnon, C.C., Wehrmann, K., Klöppel, S., & Peter, J. (2019). Incidental Learning: A Systematic Review of its effect on episodic memory performance in older age. *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience*, 11: 173. doi: [10.3389/fnagi.2019.00173](https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2019.00173)
- Whatley, M. C., Schwartz, S. T., Block, J. B., & Castel, A. D. (2023). Memory, metamemory, and false memory for features of the Apple logo. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 37(5), 904–918. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acp.4088>
- Wolfe, J.M. (1999). Inattentional amnesia. In V. Coltheart (Ed.), *Fleeting memories: Cognition of brief visual stimuli* (pp. 71–94). The MIT Press.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary Material (supporting files)

Supplementary Material 1: The rubric used in the Study 1 (Recall task)

Supplementary Material 2: Images used in the Naming Task (Study 2)

Supplementary Material 3: Protocol (in Spanish and English) used in Recall, Recognition (Study 1)

Supplementary Material 4: Protocol (in Spanish and English) used in the Naming task (Study 2)